

**A Systematic Approach to Functional Safety in an
Olefins Plant**

White Paper

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Abstract

Functional safety in a petrochemical plant is essential to ensure the safe operation of highly risky processes and minimize the likelihood of catastrophic accidents. Petrochemical facilities such as olefins plants are industrial sites that transform crude oil and natural gas into a wide range of chemical and polymer products, such as plastics, detergents, adhesives, rubber, and food items. This process operates under extreme conditions and high temperatures and employs complex processes to convert raw and intermediate materials into intermediate and final products. Potential consequences such as fire and explosion, inadvertent chemical spills, confined space hazards, corrosion, and electrical threats exemplify some risks associated. This study analyzes the key aspects that make up an effective functional safety system, in accordance with standards such as IEC 61508 and IEC 61511. The most relevant elements include the identification of safety instrumented functions (SIFs), the determination of the safety integrity level (SIL), and the design and implementation of safety instrumented systems (SIS). In addition, safety lifecycle management, risk analysis, functional validation, and periodic maintenance and testing procedures are addressed. The integration of these elements not only reduces operational risks but also improves reliability, availability, and regulatory compliance at critical facilities. This systematic approach enables petrochemical plants to operate with a higher level of protection for people, the environment, and assets.

Introduction

Day by day, functional safety has become essential in petrochemical facilities, considering that it is the best alternative to set safety goals to allocate, reduce, or mitigate any risks that might occur from possible hazards caused by the failure or unintended behavior of a system or equipment. Implementing protective measures for protecting workers, assets, and the environment has significant health, safety, financial, and environmental consequences. Incidents involving process safety have the potential to become catastrophic, resulting in fatalities, harming the environment, and compromising the assets and reputations of businesses.

Regulators, technical standards, and Recognized And Generally Accepted Good Engineering Practices (RAGAGEP), have been put in place by industry to prevent these incidents. Unfortunately, despite these efforts, accidents in petrochemical facilities are still occurring. They are continuously been reported by sources such as the Chemical Safety Board (www.csb.gov), Industrial Safety and Security Source (www.issource.com) or Anatomy of an Incident (www.anatomyofanincident.com). Williams Geismar Olefins Plant Explosion and Fire, LA (2013), PC Group Plant Fire, TX (2019) or Shell Deer Park Chemical Fire, TX (2023) are good instances of these unfortunate events.

Petrochemical facilities such as olefins plants are industrial sites that transform crude oil and natural gas into a wide range of chemical and polymer products, such as plastics,

detergents, adhesives, rubber, and food items. The olefins can be produced by steam cracking, fluid catalytic cracking of naphtha, direct/indirect conversion of synthesis gas ($\text{CO} + \text{H}_2$) or by hydrogenation of CO_2 using H_2 from renewable energy sources. This process operates under extreme conditions and high temperatures and employs complex processes to convert raw and intermediate materials into intermediate and final products. Potential consequences such as fire and explosion, inadvertent chemical spills, confined space hazards, corrosion, and electrical threats exemplify some risks associated.

Steam cracking furnaces, steam generators, boilers, caustic scrubbers, gas turbine-compressors, heat exchangers, and storage tanks are among the key pieces of equipment in an olefin plant. Housekeeping and tripping risks on process instruments and equipment must be addressed as soon as they are identified to ensure safety. While it is a challenge for safety leadership, rapid response to dangers emphasizes the importance of safety and health.

Figure 1. Process flow diagram of an Olefin Plant. [13]

There is a list of potential safety risks that can be easily identified in this type of plant:

- **Fire and Explosion**

There is serious risk of fires and explosions in olefin operations when flammable liquids, gases, and vapors are present. Hot work, electrical equipment, and chemical reactions such as thermal/catalytic cracking, hydrogenation, isomerization at high temperatures

(800- 920°C) are ignition sources that can cause catastrophic events that result in property damage, injuries, and fatalities.

- **High-Pressure activities**

There is inherent safety issues associated with high-pressure operations including cracking furnace, gas compressors, distillation columns, cold boxes, reactors, and pipelines. Hazardous material discharges, fires, or explosions can be caused by equipment malfunctions, over pressurization, and process disturbances.

- **Chemical Exposure**

During handling, processing, or maintenance tasks, employees are potentially exposed to combustible, poisonous, or corrosive materials. Chemical burns, breathing issues, skin irritation, and long-term health consequences can all arise from chemical exposure, underscoring the significance of appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE), training, and hazard communication procedures.

- **Process Safety Incidents**

Chemical spills, releases, high pressure boil-off compressors during startup, and runaway reactions in ethylene converters onsite are illustrations of process safety accidents that provide significant threats to people, property, and the environment. Process safety events can be caused by several things, including human error, poor safety culture, maintenance deficiency, and process variations.

- **Mechanical failures**

Common safety risks cover mechanical equipment leaks, ruptures, and breakdowns, such as mechanical pump seal failure, improper or inadequate lubrication that can cause overheating and damage moving parts, which can shorten the machinery's useful life. Equipment integrity can be compromised by corrosion, aging infrastructure, and poor maintenance, which can cause operational disruptions and setbacks.

- **Confined Space risks**

Special safety hazards are associated with enclosed spaces, such as pipelines, tanks, and vessels. Oxygen deficiency, hazardous atmospheres, combustible gases, and trapping hazards are among the hazards associated with confined spaces.

A 1968 American Insurance Association study of 317 large loss chemical plant explosions and fires in a 20-year period showed the following critical factors:

- a. Equipment failures were critical in 31% of the cases.
- b. Operational failures were key in 17.2% of the accidents.
- c. Weak Safety Programs were an issue in 8% of the cases. [2]

According to the Ethylene Producer Committee (EPC), olefin units accounted for 26 of the 170 major hydrocarbon property losses in the last 30 years, with a total impact of \$7.16 billion dollars.

Figure 2. Chemical incident tracking 2021-2023. November 2023 [9]

To gain further insight into addressing additional identified hazards, several critical aspects of the processes must be considered:

1. **Risk Assessment:** Identifying and Mitigating Hazards

Process safety is an interdisciplinary field of engineering that examines, prevents, and manages large-scale fires, explosions, and chemical accidents, including toxic gas releases, in facilities, both onshore and offshore, managing them by putting in place the proper safeguards to lessen the frequency and severity of accidents and learning from incidents as they occur.

Functional safety is a component of total plant and equipment safety that is dependent on the proper operation of safety-related systems as well as other risk-reduction strategies such as key procedures.

Process Hazard Analysis (PHA) is an essential safety assessment method used in industrial processes. This methodology includes the Hazard and Operability Study (HAZOP) and the Layer of Protection Analysis LOPA and their integration and how they

apply across the lifecycle of a facility from design to operations and continuous safety evaluations.

- HAZOP (Hazard and Operability Study):

According to the Center for Chemical Process Safety (CCPS), a Hazard and Operability Study (HAZOP) is a systematic qualitative technique to identify process hazards and potential operating problems using a series of guidewords to study process deviations. It requires the collaboration of a multidisciplinary team (process, operations, automation, maintenance, supervision and safety). The team should be trained in the HAZOP methodology and have a clear understanding of the system or process being analyzed to identify potential hazards operability issues and to propose preventive actions.

A HAZOP is used to question every step of a process to determine what deviations from the intention of design can take place and what their causes and implications may be. This is carried out systematically by using appropriate guidewords. This is a systematic, detailed review technique for batch and continuous plants that can be used to detect hazards in new or current procedures. Systematically examines deviations and monitors possible hazards during regular operations, startup, shutdown, or maintenance (for example, temperature spikes and valve failures).

- LOPA (Layer of Protection Analysis): A LOPA follows HAZOP and is developed based on a risk identification analysis. A HAZOP or other risk identification analysis serves as the foundation for a LOPA. By CCPS requirement, these mitigating safety measures or "layers of protection," shall be Independent Protection Layers (IPL). Relief valves and rupture disks are both instances of components that, on their own, reduce the likelihood of the hazard evolving into a full-scale event with a negative outcome. These studies are used to create Safety Instrumented Systems (SIS) that are suited to the facility's specific hazards.

Figure 3. Layers of Protection Example Visual. [17]

The requirements for Independent Protection Layers (IPL) are:

1. Specifically designed to prevent the consequence
2. Independent of the initiating event of the scenario and all other layers that are used for that same scenario
3. Dependable in terms of having sufficient defense against random and systematic failures.

Random and systematic failures are two distinct types of failures that can occur in systems, equipment, or processes. Random failures are unpredictable and occur at random times, often due to hardware degradation or external factors. Systematic failures, on the other hand, are caused by flaws in design, manufacturing, or operational procedures, lack of competency or training and can be eliminated by addressing the root cause.

4. Auditable in terms of being able to be tested and maintained

Some examples of IPLs are:

- Inherently Safer Design
- Basic Process Control System (BPCS)
- Alarm & Operator Intervention

- Safety Instrumented System (SIS)
 - Physical Detection Devices
 - Passive Devices (e.g. mechanical relief)
2. **Safety Instrumented Function (SIF), Safety Instrumented Systems (SIS) and Safety Integrity Level (SIL)**

A Safety Instrumented Function (SIF) consists of a set of equipment such as sensors, logic solver, final control elements **and all necessary interfaces** (cables, tubing, process connection, etc.), with a certain architecture (1oo1, 1oo2, 2oo3, etc.), that act together to detect a hazard and bring the process to a safe state, when specified conditions are violated; permitting a process to move forward in a safe manner when specified conditions allow (permissive functions) or taking action to mitigate the consequences of an industrial hazard.

Informally, it is a function that doesn't require operator intervention.

Common misunderstandings concerning a SIF include:

- Generating an operator alarm indication is a SIF
- Detecting an over temperature on the burner exhaust is a SIF
- Detecting a flammable gas cloud is a SIF
- Detecting smoke or fire is a SIF

None of the states mentioned above incorporate an action linked to a final element that autonomously transitions the plant to a safe state; therefore, they are not classified as a Safety Instrumented Function (SIF). They may contribute to overall risk reduction; for instance, partial credit may be assigned for the operator alarm, considering the alarm rationalization process. However, this does not constitute a Safety Instrumented Function (SIF).

Some examples of SIFs in olefin plants include:

- Flame-out in a flare system may result in the emission of unburnt flammable and/or toxic waste gases cause process gas feed to be shut off. The automatic protective action is to close gas feed to the flare, which stops any toxic gas release, bringing the system to a safe state.
- Flame-out in a boiler that could cause fuel gas accumulation and explosion resulting in a main fuel gas trip. The automatic instrument protection action is a main fuel gas trip, which cuts off the fuel and prevents fuel gas accumulation, bringing the system to a safe state.
- High pressure in a vessel opens a vent valve that can lead to overpressure in the vessel. The high pressure is detected by a pressure-sensing instrument, and logic

- (PLC, relay, hardwired, etc.) opens a vent valve, bringing the system to a safe state.
- High temperature in a reactor can lead to a runaway reaction. A temperature sensor detects excessive temperatures. When the temperature exceeds a setpoint, the logic solver initiates a fuel trip or cooling fluid shutdown to prevent overheating and potential damage.
 - High temperature in a furnace can cause tube rupture to shut off firing to the furnace. The specific hazard is tube rupture. Instrumentation automatically causes a main fuel trip that removes the heat, bringing the system to a safe state.

Safety Instrumented Systems (SIS) usually have a few SIFs with different safety integrity levels (SIL), so it is best to avoid describing it by a single SIL. A SIS utilizes several SIF's working together as a whole to protect the entire plant.

Figure 5. Safety Instrument Systems [14]

The safety instrumented functions (SIFs) of a SIS are designed to automatically implement corrective measures, such as the shutdown of an equipment, if unsafe conditions are identified. Determining the SIL is a measure of the performance required from a SIF to maintain or achieve the safety state.

Safety Integrity Levels (SILs) (1–4) are assigned to each SIF in accordance with the necessary risk reduction, and compliance with IEC 61511. Each SIL represents an order of magnitude risk reduction, where the associated risk reduction increases as the levels increase (see figure 4 below). The higher the Safety Integrity Level, the greater the impact or consequence of a failure, and the lower the failure rate that is acceptable.

This measure consists of two fundamental elements:

- Hardware safety integrity is generally assessed based on random hardware failures, which can typically be estimated with a reasonable degree of accuracy using the probability of failure on demand (PFD).
- Systematic safety integrity is often more challenging to quantify. The diversity of failure causes is significant; systematic failures can arise during the specification, design, implementation, operational, and modification phases, impacting both hardware and software.

The determination of a target Safety Integrity Level (SIL) for the process must be based on an assessment of the likelihood of incident occurrence and the potential consequences of such incidents.

Figure 4. Safety Integrity levels.

SIL	PFD avg		RRF	
	\geq	$<$	$>$	\leq
SIL-1	0,01	0,1	10	100
SIL-2	0,001	0,01	100	1000
SIL-3	0,0001	0,001	1000	10000
SIL-4	0,00001	0,0001	10000	100000

Figure 5. Safety Integrity Levels vs. PFD avg (low demand mode)

For example, in a SIF with SIL-1 we will reduce the risk by a minimum of 10 times, with SIL-2 100 times and with SIL-3 1000 times.

IEC 61511 requires all equipment used in a SIS to be justified. IEC 61511 allows for two methods of justification: 1) Use of IEC 61508 certified devices, and 2) Prior use justification. Typically, the process involves ensuring only SIL-capable devices from reputable suppliers. In situations where a risk assessment does not necessitate SIL suitability, field and interface devices are being utilized more frequently. Utilizing a single, consistent device type facilitates maintenance and prevents confusion between devices that are SIL-suitable and those that are not. Where SIL-capable devices are unavailable, justifying the use of the equipment on prior use is recommended.

Today, approximately two-thirds of the interface devices that are delivered to the olefin plant shall be for SIL 2 or SIL 3.

Some recommendations for olefin plants are:

- ✓ Prevention of excessive polymerization or runaway reactions: a SIL 2 SIFs-rated may regulate temperature such as diolefins converters or cracking furnaces.
- ✓ Leakage: SIL 3 SIFs may be implemented for emergency isolation of ethylene pipelines.

3. Redundancy and Fault-Tolerant Design

To avoid single points of failure, SIS components (sensors, logic solvers, valves) incorporate redundancy. A 2-out-of-3 voting system involves more components, increases input/output (I/O) requirements and power consumption, and is commonly seen in applications like gas turbines, compressors and heaters, and critical equipment in olefins plants.

For instance, 2oo3 ensures two sensors must detect a hazard before triggering a shutdown, balancing safety and availability (e.g. false trip prevention). This architecture reduces both the spurious trip rate and average PFD.

4. Testing, Maintenance, and Proof Testing

Routine proof testing verifies the performance of the Safety Instrumented System (SIS). For instance, simulating a high-pressure situation to confirm the proper closure of shutdown valves. Predictive and routine maintenance plays a fundamental role due to the periodic inspection of equipment aids to evaluate mechanical integrity, check valves and vibration analysis or thermography, which mitigates equipment deterioration in adverse situations.

5. Operator Training and Human Factors

Even advanced systems rely on human intervention. Training programs should cover emergency response protocols (e.g., leak containment), interpreting alarms and manual overrides, and reducing human error through ergonomic control room design and clear

procedures is equally vital. If electrical dangers are not adequately controlled, they could contribute to accidents and multiples fatalities.

Businesses should prioritize minimizing risks and establishing a secure workplace for workers, and there are measures that can be taken to ensure their electrical procedures are optimized. You can maintain employee safety and seamless operations by putting programs like electrical safety training, arc flash evaluations, and infrared surveys into place.

6. Compliance and Documentation

Documentation risk assessments, SIL verification and maintenance records are mandatory for audits and compliance. They provide evidence of the SIS's functionality, performance, and adherence to relevant standards like IEC 61511 (it is currently a requirement in the 2016 edition) and ISA/IEC61511. Meeting IEC 61511 requirements emphasizes the need for ongoing verification and maintenance of SIS performance through continuous monitoring and testing.

Similarly, digital tools streamline record-keeping and traceability but must be suitable for the application and qualified appropriately.

7. Emergency Shutdown (ESD) and Isolation Systems

Rapid response systems are critical in olefins plants. Emergency Shutdown (ESD) is the most critical shutdown mode used in petrochemical facilities. It is designed to immediately halt operations in the event of severe hazard or imminent danger. The primary goal of an ESD is to protect human life, the environment, and the facility itself. For this reason, it is vital to install and maintain ESD systems to quickly and safely shut down the plant in case of an emergency.

Steam cracking furnace operations are typically associated with overpressure, which can be hazardous and complex to control. In severe operating conditions, such as overpressure, the safe venting of hydrocarbons using an ESD system will cut off the supply and vent the lines. Solenoid valves function as an upstream link between the electrical control system and the pneumatic actuator. They are controlled by electromagnets and can switch rapidly.

Solenoid drivers prevent compatibility problems between the field device and the diagnostics of the digital output (DO) cards in the emergency shut down system and sensors monitor the shutdown. In addition, acoustic and visual warning systems, and fire extinguishing devices must be activated in an emergency. Safety relays are used to activate these systems.

8. Fire and Gas Detection Systems:

A Fire and Gas Detection System (F&G) is a widely used Safety Integrity System (SIS) that detects fire or combustible/toxic gas leaks and takes action to minimize the danger and prevent it from turning into a fire, explosion, or gas releases. Trigger deluge systems and isolating fuel sources during fires are good representation of these types of systems. These F&G systems should be hard-wired into the ESD system and emergency response procedures.

F&G detection devices have improved greatly during the last years. Detection rates, response time and spurious alarms were improved by new techniques, by adding intelligence to the equipment. SIL certification according to IEC-61511 standards is also an important addition for a F&G as a SIS. Having at hand the advanced and certified field equipment as well as central units on the market, it is possible to design and implement integrated systems covering all the control and safe requirements withal taking advantage of all benefits of an integrated BPCS - SIS solution.

9. Management of Change (MOC):

Process safety management program weaknesses include MOC, Pre-Startup Safety Review and PHA. Deviations from the process sequence in olefin plants often represent dangerous errors, requiring SIFs with SIL 3 target.

Implementing a robust MOC process to assess and manage properly changes to the plant's processes, equipment, or safety systems will prevent incidents, additionally ensuring that any changes do not compromise the plant's functional safety.

10. Cybersecurity for Safety Systems

As SIS integrates with Operational Technology (OT) networks, safeguarding against cyber-attacks is essential. A security solution would be that all engineering workstations must be secured and should only be connected to a safety network through a Firewall when connecting to the Process Control Network (PCN). However, it is important to ensure that the firewall is properly configured and deployed to protect against unauthorized changes and vulnerabilities.

All methods of mobile data transfer to the isolated safety network, including CDs, USB drives, and DVDs, must be scanned prior to utilization in engineering workstations or any node linked to this network.

Laptops and PCs must be thoroughly tested for viruses and malware prior to connecting to the secure network or any safety controller.

Safety systems must consistently be implemented on isolated networks. Strategies encompass network segmentation and compliance with IEC 62443 standards.

11. Incident Investigation and continuous monitoring:

Investigate incidents and near-misses to determine root causes are a cornerstone of continuous improvement in safety-critical environments, particularly olefin plants. By systematically analyzing incidents ranging from minor near-misses to major accident organizations can identify root causes, implement corrective actions, and foster a culture of learning and accountability:

- ✓ **Root Cause Analysis Techniques:** investigations go beyond surface-level symptoms to uncover underlying systemic issues. Techniques like the “5 Whys,” fishbone diagrams, fault trees analysis and failure mode within the SIS components (dangerous or safe, random or systematic) and Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) help identify the true causes of incidents, enabling organizations to address the source rather than just the effects.
- ✓ **Safety Function Performance:** continuous monitoring ensures that the Safety Instrumented Functions (SIF) are available and can perform their intended safety function on demand, achieving the desired Safety Integrity Level (SIL).
- ✓ **Reliability:** by identifying and addressing failures promptly, continuous monitoring contributes to the overall reliability and availability of the SIS.
- ✓ **Preventing Recurrence:** stage 4 of the Safety Lifecycle of the IEC 61511 involves continuous monitoring under the Operation and Maintenance phase. This stage focuses on maintaining the safety system's integrity during operation.

By implementing corrective actions based on findings such as diagnostics to evaluate functionality and report any detected faults, software check to ensure correct program execution and data integrity, regular verification of communication links of the SIS to ensure data exchange and responsiveness and monitoring process variables, can determine whether a SIF has been activated or is in a potentially unsafe state.

12. Enhancing Safety Programs

Analyzing incident data allows organizations to refine their safety protocols, training programs, and workplace practices, leading to improved safety performance.

13. Promoting a Safety Culture

Thorough investigations demonstrate a commitment to learning and improvement, fostering trust among employees and encouraging reporting without fear of retribution.

14. Continuous Learning and Adaptation

Regular post-incident reviews allow organizations to evaluate the effectiveness of their responses, identify areas for improvement, and make incremental changes that lead to long-term efficiency.

Example: A Safety instrumented System (SIS) failure:

Conclusion

Numerous safety hazards are inherent in the operations of the olefin facilities. Organizations shall address specific safety measures in place to safeguard people, property, and the environment by recognizing and preventing the most frequent safety risks, such as chemical exposure, fire and explosion hazards, process safety incidents, mechanical equipment failures, confined space hazards and high-pressure operations.

A comprehensive strategy that combines strong engineering, proactive maintenance, trained staff, and flexible tactics is required for functional safety in olefin facilities. Operators can guarantee not only regulatory compliance but also the long-term viability and dependability of their facilities. By giving priority to these factors, it will preserve the company's standing as a responsible and safe operator.

This will lead to an increase in trust among all parties involved, such as the community, consumers, and regulators. Functional safety is more than just a necessity in a field where the stakes are extremely high. It's a dedication to protecting livelihoods and lives.

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exida – Who we are.

exida is one of the world's leading accredited certification and knowledge companies specializing in automation system cybersecurity, safety, and availability. Founded in 2000 by several of the world's top reliability and safety experts, *exida* is a global company with offices around the world. *exida* offers training, coaching, project-oriented consulting services, standalone and internet-based safety and cybersecurity engineering tools, detailed product assurance and certification analysis, and a collection of online safety, reliability, and cybersecurity resources. *exida* maintains a comprehensive failure rate and failure mode database on electrical and mechanical components, as well as automation equipment based on hundreds of field failure data sets representing over 350 billion unit operating hours.

exida Certification is an ANSI (American National Standards Institute) accredited independent certification organization that performs functional safety (IEC 61508 family of standards) and cybersecurity (IEC 62443 family of standards) certification assessments.

exida Engineering provides the users of automation systems with the knowledge to cost-effectively implement automation system cybersecurity, safety, and high availability solutions. The *exida* team will solve complex issues in the fields of functional safety, cybersecurity, and alarm management, like unique voting arrangement analysis, quantitative consequence analysis, or rare event likelihood analysis, and stands ready to assist when needed.

Training

exida believes that safety, high availability, and cybersecurity are achieved when more people understand the topics. Therefore, *exida* has developed a successful training suite of online, on-demand, and web-based instructor-led courses and on-site training provided either as part of a project or by standard courses. The course content and subjects range from introductory to advanced. The *exida* website lists the continuous range of courses offered around the world.

Knowledge Products

exida Innovation has made the process of designing, installing, and maintaining a safety and high availability automation system easier, as well as providing a practical methodology for managing cybersecurity across the entire lifecycle. Years of experience in the industry have allowed a crystallization of the combined knowledge that is converted into useful tools and documents, called knowledge products. Knowledge products include procedures for implementing cybersecurity, the Safety Lifecycle tasks, software tools, and templates for all phases of design.

Tools and Products for End User Support

- exSILentia® – Integrated Safety Lifecycle Tool
 - PHAx™ (Process Hazard Analysis)
 - LOPAx™ (Layer of Protection Analysis)

excellence in dependable automation

- SILAlarm™ (Alarm Management and Rationalization)
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- Process SRS (PHA based Safety Requirements Specification definition)
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- Design SRS (Conceptual Design based Safety Requirements Specification definition)
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- ARCHx (System Analysis tool; Hardware and Software Failure, Dependent Failure, and Cyber Threat Analysis)

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